

Vitamin K and the Clotting of Blood

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Vitamin K mediates the formation of active prothrombin inside the liver, from the physiologically inactive precursor protein through the post ribosomal modification occurring after the completion of the synthesis of the polypeptide chain of the precursor. The activity of vitamin K centers round the formation of ten additional carboxyl groups attached to one each of the gamma (γ)-carbon atom of the ten glutamic acid residues situated towards the N-terminal region of the prothrombin molecule at positions 7, 8, 15, 17, 20, 21, 26, 27, 30 and 33. This carboxylated fragment I of the normal prothrombin molecule having the ten γ -carboxylglutamic acid residues in the chain of 42 amino acids at positions 1 to 42, is responsible for binding calcium ions and subsequent complexing with phospholipids and advancing proper conformation so that the prothrombin molecule may interact suitably with the physiological activators and is cleaved at the peptide bonds located between arginine and threonine at positions 274-275, as well as the bond between arginine and isoleucine at positions 323-324 to be activated to thrombin which subsequently converts the circulating fibrinogen to fibrin. The reactivity of vitamin K is exerted through its formation of a reduced intermediate.

WHEN blood is shed, it clots almost immediately. Filud blood may even clot inside the blood vessels within the living body under pathological conditions. Fluidity of blood inside the blood vessels is necessary to carry out its normal functions. On the other hand, clot formation or hemostasis is necessary at the spot of injury to prevent further loss of blood. Accordingly, the formation of clot inside the blood vessels, as well as the absence of clot formation at the spot of an injury, is to be taken as abnormalities in the normal reaction of blood clotting process.

The Clotting of Blood :

The mechanism of clot formation inside a blood vessel or its formation at any spot of an external injury has been represented by two different pathways¹⁻³. In the extrinsic mechanism, the prime mover of the clotting process is the product from the injured tissue ; whereas in the intrinsic mechanism the different factors present in blood undergo a chain of chemical and enzymatic reactions, ultimately producing a product similar to the component produced by the injured tissue.

Normal human blood is supposed to contain twelve clotting factors, factors I to XIII, (claim for the presence of a factor, factor VI, has been ruled out). In a series of reactions in which factor XII (Hageman factor) is activated primarily by any rough surface, the chain reaction starts. The activated product then reacts with the next factor. Each activated product formed from its precursor, reacts in its turn producing in each case, a corresponding activated product, which then reacts with the next factor and the chain process continues until factor X of blood is acted upon, and corresponding enzyme, activated

factor X, factor X_a, with thrombokinase activity⁴ as it was formerly called, is formed (Fig. 1). Factor X_a in presence of calcium ion, phospholipid and

Fig. 1. Clotting of blood. Phase I, Formation of thrombokinase activity from Stuart Prower factor (factor X→X_a). Phase II, Formation of Thrombin from Prothrombin (factor II→IIa). Phase III, Formation of Fibrin from fibrinogen (Factor I→Ia).

factor V splits prothrombin when the profragment of the prothrombin molecule is left out (Fig. 2), and the prethrombin chain with potential thrombin activity is produced. Factor X_a then splits a second peptide bond in the prethrombin 2 (also termed intermediate 2) whereby the single-chained product is converted to a double-chained compound, joined through the disulphide bridge (Fig. 2).

In the extrinsic pathway, the tissue product or thromboplastin (factor III) which is a lipo-protein, is involved. It has enzymatic properties and activates factor VII of blood to its activated form. The product VIIa then reacts along with other accessory factors on factor X and then enzyme activity, factor X_a activity, for reacting with the prothrombin molecule is developed. Russell's viper venom in presence of Ca²⁺ can react directly with factor X of the blood to produce X_b⁵. The pathway following the formation of factor X_a is common both to the intrinsic and extrinsic mechanisms.

Thrombin is a serine protease. It has esterase activity also. It acts on the circulating fibrinogen (factor I) and splits it whereby some peptides are left out and fibrin monomer is formed. Fibrin monomer polymerises to produce fibrin polymer, which in the presence of Ca²⁺ and factor XIII of blood, produces cross-linked urea-insoluble polymer⁶. The network of fibrin polymer entraps the formed elements of blood. Fibrin, even after its formation, may be

lysed by plasmin which is produced from its precursor (Fig. 1). However, if the equilibrium is shifted towards the formation of the cross-linked fibrin, the blood-clot is produced (Fig.1)¹⁻⁶.

Prothrombin Molecule and its Cleavage :

The prothrombin molecule present in the circulating blood of different species of animals is more or less similar and varies slightly in details of amino acid sequence in certain, not very significant, region and also in their numbers. Although the structure of bovine prothrombin has been the focus of investigations for the last few years, studies on prothrombin and its structure have also been undertaken with blood samples obtained from various sources with abnormalities in their blood factors and having coagulation defects⁷. The structure of human and rat prothrombin has been investigated especially with a view to finding the effect of different anticoagulant drugs, viz., coumarins and warfarin respectively.

Bovine prothrombin consists of single polypeptide chain of 582 amino acid residues with N-terminal alanine (Fig. 2). The complete amino acid sequence of bovine prothrombin has been reported by Magnuson *et al.*⁸ Prothrombin contains 12-disulphide bridges. Fragment I has five bridges connecting half cystines and the fragment 2 has three. One bridge connects the A and B chains of thrombin

Fig. 2. The prothrombin molecule (after Magnusson *et al.*⁸) and its cleavage. The loop is not shown in the line 2 & 3. Line 1, Cleavage by Thrombin at 156-157 (Arg-Ser). Line 3. Cleavage at Arg-274, Thr-275 by factor X_a Line 4. Cleavage by factor X_a to produce Thrombin A chain and B. Chains

whereas three are internal in the B chain of thrombin⁹. Some of the half cystines connect themselves to form kringlelike structure in some region of the prothrombin molecule (Fig. 3). Prothrombin contains a total of approx. 12% carbohydrate consisting of glucosamine, mannose, galactose and sialic acid, attached as three oligosaccharide units to asparagine residues 77, 101 and 376 (Fig. 2 & 3)^{8, 9}.

Hemker *et al.*¹⁰ isolated from rat liver microsomes a form of prothrombin which is produced in the absence of vitamin K. This form of prothrombin which is produced in the absence of vitamin K or in the presence of its antagonists has been named PIVKA prothrombin, i.e., prothrombin induced by vitamin K absence or antagonists (PIVKA). It has been later shown by Shah & Suttie¹¹ and

Fig. 3. Fragment 1.2, amino acid upto the portion 274 (after Magnusson *et al.*⁹) of the prothrombin molecule. N-terminal region binds Ca^{2+} ion in the γ -carboxy glutamic acid residues, represented by circles with forks. Joined circles: disulphide bridges. Diamonds: carbohydrate.

During activation, in presence of factor X_a , the prothrombin molecule cleaved to give fraction 1.2 and the intermediate 2 (Prethrombin 2), which is then further cleaved by X_a in presence of factor V_a (in addition to phospholipid, Ca^{2+}) to give the A and B chain of thrombin (Fig. 2).

From the studies of interaction of prothrombin molecule it seems that entire prothrombin molecule participates obligatorily in the formation of the fibrinogen splitting enzyme thrombin, although the prethrombin 2 (Intermediate 2) is the portion of the molecule which contains the potential enzyme activity. The prethrombin which is produced after the cleavage of fragment 1.2 is again cleaved in its turn to a double chain protein, A and B chain, joined by the disulphide bridge. The profragment (Fragment 1.2) participates in the activation process, via (i) fragment I region, which combines with Ca^{2+} and phospholipid and (ii) through fragment 2 region, having its participation with factor V_a . In addition to this interaction, fragment 1.2 (profragment) noncovalently attaches itself to prethrombin 2 (Intermediate 2), when it is further reacted upon by factor X_a in presence of lipid and factor V_a during which single chain prethrombin is converted to the double-chained thrombin in which A chain and B chain are joined through a disulphide bridge.

others¹² to be the precursor which may be converted to normal prothrombin in presence of vitamin K and its analogs.

Echis carinatus venom can convert the inactive prothrombin, whereas physiological activator, viz., factor X_a cannot produce thrombin from the inactive prothrombin¹³. The inactive prothrombin is not adsorbed on barium citrate or cannot bind calcium to the same degree as normal prothrombin¹⁴. These differences are due to the development of certain property in normal prothrombin which has developed as a result of vitamin K action which is needed to produce the calcium-binding site and responsible for the barium citrate adsorption and also to develop the physiological activity so as to function as the active prothrombin. Vitamin K acts chemically and alters the inactive prothrombin to its active form.

Vitamin K:

Although both vitamin K_1 and K_2 series are known to be antihemorrhagic, most of the works have been concentrated around vitamin K_1 . Several synthetic analogs have been prepared, having antihemorrhagic activities^{15, 16}. Those and some of the other naturally occurring similar compounds have been found to be effective¹⁶. Vitamin K_1 , (Fig. 6)

2-methyl 3-phytyl 1,4 naphthaquinone (phylloquinone series) and K_8 , 2-methyl-3-farnesylfarnesyl 1,4 naphthaquinone (menaquinone series) and menadi-one have been found to be effective as vitamin K drugs. Based on the normalization of the prolonged blood clotting time in vitamin K deficient chickens, the biological activity of phylloquinone and menaquinone was found to be dependent on the length of side chain. Vitamin K compounds with 20 or 25 carbon atoms in the side chain are the most active ones when administered orally¹⁷. When the methyl group is substituted by chloride, vitamin K antagonist property is developed and the compound 2-chloro 3-phytyl 1,4 naphthaquinone (Cl-K) inhibits the vitamin K activity¹⁸.

When the anticoagulants are administered, normal prothrombin is not found in the circulating plasma. Physiologically inactive protein has been purified from the dicoumarol treated cows to high purity^{19,20}. It is very similar to normal prothrombin in its carboxylate, amino acid composition, its ability to be activated by several nonphysiological activators, for example, venom of the Indian viperid *Echis carinatus* venom^{1,8} mentioned earlier and trypsin²⁰.

Mode of Action of Vitamin K :

Vitamin K acts on a carboxylase system present in liver microsomes to incorporate additional carboxy group on some of the glutamic acid residues (ten in number) at the N-terminal region of the fragment I of the prothrombin molecule²¹ (Fig. 3). These ten gamma carboxyglutamic acid residues are responsible for binding Ca^{2+} which in its turn binds the phospholipid to give rise to the correct conformation of the prothrombin molecule to interact with physiological activator, viz., factor X_a ^{22,26}. In the absence of vitamin K or in the presence of vitamin K antagonists, the incorporation of additional carboxyl groups to these glutamic acid residues of the prothrombin molecule is not effected; and the subsequent activation towards the cleavage of the prothrombin molecule does not occur^{23,24}.

Sadowski *et al.*²⁵ showed that vitamin K is required for an enzymatic carboxylation of glutamyl residue in the microsomal precursor of plasma prothrombin to form γ -carboxyglutamic acid. This carboxylase enzyme system has been shown to catalyse CO_2 fixation or HCO_3^- incorporation in the glutamic acid residues to produce the biologically active prothrombin²⁶. The enzyme activity requires oxygen and vitamin K hydroquinone or vitamin K+NADPH²⁷. It is suggested that the energy required for carboxylation reaction is derived from oxidation of the reduced form of vitamin K^{23,27} :

Although the activity of warfarin and chloro-K (Cl-K) inhibits the carboxylase system, they slightly differ in their action. Chloro-K (Cl-K) effectively inhibits both the membrane and soluble

carboxylase; warfarin inhibits only the membrane-bound carboxylase^{25,27}. Previously it was believed that the incorporation of the carboxyl group is effected post-translationally by a reaction which requires vitamin K^{21,23,28}. It has been shown that postmitochondrial supernatants from vitamin K deficient rats incorporate added $H^{14}CO_3^-$ into microsomal proteins upon the addition of vitamin K²⁶. Work on vitamin K-dependent *in vitro*-system that produces prothrombin, has shown²⁹ that postmitochondrial supernatants from vitamin K deficient rat respond to the addition of vitamin K by producing significant amount of prothrombin, as assayed by the two stage assay. Prothrombin production is dependent on O_2 and the energy supply; and vitamin K-dependent step in prothrombin synthesis has been shown to be the formation of γ -carboxyglutamic acid (Fig. 6.) residues, which is only effected in the fragment I region of prothrombin^{21,32}. This fact has been conclusively demonstrated by the radioactivity measured after the incorporation of $H^{14}CO_3^-$ in isolated systems²⁶.

The vitamin K-dependent carboxylase system :

Liver microsomes require the presence of prothrombin precursor, O_2 , vitamin K and HCO_3^- , and are stimulated by energy source and factor present in postmicrosomal supernatant in the protein acting as a NAD^+ , ($NADP^+$)-reductase²³. This requirement can be replaced with the addition of NADH or NADPH to the system and the requirement for reducing equivalents from pyridine nucleotides in the system has now been shown to be largely a requirement for the reduced form of vitamin K^{25,33}.

Although it has been established firmly that vitamin K mediates the carboxylation of ten glutamic acid residues to γ -carboxyglutamic acids in the fragment I of the prothrombin molecule situated by the N-terminal region of the molecule, the way in which it acts has not been established. (i). It may function by transferring CO_2 (HCO_3^-) for the carboxylation reaction; (ii) on the other hand, it may function by forming the carbonium ion so that it may accept the HCO_3^- ion. The quinone with its redox property may easily be converted to hydroquinone, which may not be physiologically stable but biologically active to trap the oxygen molecule. The discovery³⁴ that γ -carboxyglutamic acid residue is not found only in plasma proteins produced in the liver, indicates that calcium dependent enzyme systems might also be operative in those cases; γ -carboxyglutamic acid containing proteins have been demonstrated to be present in bones and renal tissues which indicate that vitamin K-dependent carboxylase system may be present in other tissues also³⁴.

Binding of Ca^{2+} :

It is known that the prothrombin which is produced in the liver in the absence of vitamin K

or with simultaneous administration of dicoumarol type of drugs, differs from normal prothrombin in that it is not adsorbed on barium citrate or is unable to bind calcium ions¹⁴. Stenflo³⁵ developed a purification method of dicoumarol-induced prothrombin and studied^{2a,36} the Ca^{2+} binding properties using equilibrium dialyses. It was found that the dicoumarol prothrombin, which is actually prothrombin precursor, is unable to bind Ca^{2+} ³⁶. The stronger Ca^{2+} binding property of normal prothrombin has been accounted for by its content of the γ -carboxyglutamic acid residues. Unless the prothrombin binds Ca^{2+} ions, it cannot interact normally with phospholipids that stimulate its activation. The rapid activation of prothrombin to thrombin catalysed by factor X_a in the presence of factor V and phospholipid, involves the formation of a Ca^{2+} dependent complex of prothrombin and phospholipid³⁷. In fact, fragment I, in general, and the γ -carboxyglutamic acid residues, in particular, play a decisive role in the complex formation³⁷. Although the prethrombin I part of the prothrombin molecule, i.e., Intermediate I, contains thrombin part of the original molecule, it can not be activated to thrombin in phospholipid dependent system, due to the fact that it does not contain fragment I which is the calcium binding part of the prothrombin molecule. Similarly, dicoumarol prothrombin which contains the fragment I but without the extra carboxyl groups, cannot be activated to thrombin in the phospholipid dependent system.

Specific enzyme present in the Indian snake venom *Echis carinatus* venom, can convert dicoumarol induced prothrombin¹⁻³ which is actually the prothrombin precursor even it does not contain extra carboxyl groups into thrombin; and venom enzyme is not dependent on Ca^{2+} for its activity, whereas Russell's viper venom which converts factor X to factor X_a , is calcium dependent³⁸. Factor X_a , which is also calcium dependent, cannot act on the prothrombin molecule, which is devoid of fragment I, i.e., on the prethrombin I part alone or on dicoumarol-induced prothrombin, which does not contain extra carboxyl group on each of the glutamic acid residues. It has been shown that calcium phospholipid binding, which is a characteristic of fragment I, is very similar to the binding of Ca^{2+} to the intact prothrombin, indicating that fragment I is the domain, which is responsible for this property of the entire prothrombin molecule³⁹. Accordingly, it can be summarised³⁹ that:

(1) Ca^{2+} ions form bridges between γ -carboxyl group in the vitamin K-dependent region of prothrombin and phosphate groups of phospholipid.

(2) Ca^{2+} ions connect the γ -carboxyglutamyl acid residues in prothrombin, changing the conformation of the region with amino acids 1-42, such that hydrophobic internal parts of the prothrombin structure are exposed; and lipid binding site is formed.

(3) The conformational change may even lead to the exposure of a hydrophobic lipid binding site in any other part of prothrombin structure, even outside the region 1-42.

The prothrombin molecule which does not normally bind phospholipid, becomes phospholipid binding even in presence of ten extra negative charges. Whether phospholipid binding is due to the attachment through Ca^{2+} or due to its influence on attaching phospholipids to some other hydrophobic portion of prothrombin molecule has not yet been ascertained.

Thrombin Catalysed Inactivation of Prothrombin Transformation Reactions:

Thrombin itself splits the prothrombin molecule into fragment I and prethrombin 1 (intermediate I) and as soon as these two portions of the prothrombin molecules are separated, further reaction is stopped. Thus thrombin catalysed negative feedback process controls the mechanism for limiting the further activation of prothrombin⁴⁰. Although the activity of thrombin on fibrinogen is not metal-dependent, the metal ions enhance the thrombin activity⁴¹. Ca^{2+} is, however, superior in its activity⁴¹, but it is not essentially needed similar to the splitting of prothrombin molecule to thrombin by factor X_a ⁴². Factor X is one of the vitamin K-dependent proteins as prothrombin⁴³. Its activation to factor X_a is also vitamin K-dependent⁴³, suggesting that Ca^{2+} is needed for their activities. The sequence determination of light and heavy chains of bovine factor X_a has shown that its heavy chain is strongly homologous to the chain of thrombin, whereas there is a high degree of homology of the light chain of factor X_a to the fragment I of prothrombin indicating that vitamin K-dependent calcium binding region has been strongly conserved during evolution⁴³ and probably functions almost identically in the two proteins; and also that the structure comprises only the region located between 1 and 42. It has been shown⁴⁴ that factor X binds with calcium which reacts with the coagulant protein of Russell's Viper Venom [RVV(X)] giving $X\text{-Ca}$.

$$-\text{RVV(X)} \text{ or } \text{Ca} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{X} \\ | \\ \diagdown \text{RVV(X)} \end{array} \text{ to be converted to the activated form, factor } X_a.$$

Factor X, even after its activation, may still retain the serine protease chain and also Ca^{2+} phospholipid binding chain, whereas in prothrombin activation, i.e., during the activation of prothrombin to thrombin, the vitamin K-dependent Ca-Phospholipid binding region and the serine protease are split into two different molecules, that is fragment I, and prethrombin I^{37, 42} (Fig.2). It may also be possible that the calcium ion mediates an artificial high concentration of the substrate (Prothrombin) molecule, by attaching itself to the phospholipid micelle, whereby the rate of prothrombin conversion increases. The dependence of factor Va for its combination⁴⁵ with fragment 2 on calcium has not been.

established. There is different opinion with regard to the effect of factor V or factor Va on prothrombin conversion^{45, 46}. Jackson *et al.*^{32, 47} have shown that when prothrombin⁹ (intermediate 2) is taken as a substrate, its activation to thrombin is dependent on factor X_a, calcium, phospholipid and also fragment 1.2. They have suggested that in an alternative pathway, factor Va may not take part in prothrombin activation⁴⁵. The increase of concentration of the substrate over phospholipid micelle may even increase the rate to such an extent, that the involvement of Va may be excluded⁴⁹.

The action of thrombin on the prothrombin molecule is not metal-dependent. It attacks the Arg-156 and Ser-157 bond of the prothrombin molecule. The portion of the prothrombin, containing calcium binding part, i.e., fragment 1, retains all its original properties, but being separated from the thrombin producing portion of the original intact molecule, it is ineffective. In fact, both the fragments, fragment 1 and fragment 2, are needed^{47, 48} to produce the necessary conformational changes in the original prothrombin molecule to expose itself towards the action of the physiological activators (Fig.4.). Jackson *et al.*^{32, 47} conclusively proved the association of prothrombin 2 by factor X_a.

Fig. 4. Activation of prothrombin 2 (Intermediate 2) in presence of different activators (X_a, V, phospholipid Ca²⁺ (after Esmon *et al.*, 47)
 ●—● without added Fragments
 ■—■ in the presence of Fragment 1.2
 ▲—▲ in the presence of both Fragment 2 and Fragment 1.

Vitamin K-epoxide : Epoxidation of Vitamin K :

Postmitochondrial supernatants from vitamin K deficient rat liver catalyze both the vitamin K dependent conversion of microsomal precursor proteins to prothrombin³³ and the conversion of vitamin K to its 2,3 epoxide³³ (Fig. 6). Vitamin K is an essential cofactor for a microsomal carboxylase that converts glutamyl residues in endogenous precursor proteins to γ -carboxyglutamyl residues in completed proteins. The same microsomal preparation con-

verts vitamin K to its 2,3 epoxide and it has been suggested that these two reactions, carboxylation and epoxidation, are coupled. It has been observed that in the presence of vitamin K antagonist a metabolite of vitamin K, which is an oxidised form of vitamin K, is produced⁵⁰. This metabolite, vitamin K 2,3 epoxide, has been originally designated as an inhibitory compound towards the carboxylation of the ten glutamic acid groups of the prothrombin precursor⁵⁰. It is now known that epoxidation and carboxylation are complementary reactions and are not antagonistic to each other^{51, 52}. It is suggested⁵² that the coumarin drugs (e.g., warfarin) does not block epoxidation by inhibiting the epoxidase enzyme of the liver microsomes ; on the other hand, it inhibits epoxide-reductase activity by which epoxide is converted to vitamin K. The cycle is thereby interrupted by the presence of these anticoagulants, whereby vitamin K cannot be revived and thus become unavailable for the acceleration of carboxylation reaction^{53, 54}. Furthermore, epoxide reductase activity being blocked, the epoxide : vitamin K ratio will increase^{50, 52}. It has been suggested that epoxide formation and the reaction incorporating additional carboxyl groups in prothrombin molecule are mediated by vitamin K through a common intermediate, a hydroquinone form^{55, 56, 58} of vitamin K (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Epoxidase and carboxylase activities (after Bell.⁵³) Interactions with antivitamin K and anticoagulants Coumarins and Indanediones inhibit reactions (3), (1) and (4) at high level. TCP and Cl-K inhibit reactions (1) or (2) or both ; (4).

Both the reactions, viz., (i) conversion of glutamyl residues, of endogenous precursor protein to γ -carboxyglutamyl residue, and (ii) the conversion of vitamin K to its 2,3 epoxide by the same microsomal preparation, have been found to be inhibited by glutathione peroxidase⁵⁴. Furthermore, in the absence of vitamin K and in the presence of NADPH, tertiary butyl hydroperoxide is an apparent competitive inhibitor of vitamin K for both the carboxylase and epoxidase reactions⁵⁴. It was thus concluded⁵⁴ that both of these vitamin K requiring reactions involve a common oxygenated intermediate, and that the hydroperoxide of the vitamin is the species involved. The epoxidation of the vitamin is inhibited by direct antagonists of the vitamin viz. tetrachloro 4-pyridinol (TCP) and 2-chloro 3-phytyl 1, 4-naphthaquinone (Cl-K) (Fig. 4) but not by coumarin anticoagulant, warfarin⁵². In general, the conditions which favour epoxide formation also stimulate the formation of prothrombin. Furthermore, epoxidation is not dependent on the HCO₃.

concentration, but prothrombin formation is dependent on the HCO_3^- concentration⁵³. Thus it may not even be possible that the epoxidation reaction is coupled in some obligatory manner to the vitamin K-dependent carboxylation which is required for prothrombin formation. Again vitamin K is converted to vitamin K hydroquinone through NADH-dehydrogenase system, which may act as the intermediate for both carboxylase and epoxidase activities⁵² (Fig. 5). The epoxide is converted to vitamin K through a epoxide-reductase system. The coumarin and indanedione drugs may block the conversion of vitamin K to its hydroquinone by acting on the dehydrogenase system. It may also block the carboxylase system which converts glutamic acid to γ -carboxyglutamic acid through the incorporation of CO_2 or HCO_3^- .

Fig. 6. Vitamin K₁, K₁-epoxide, glutamic acid, γ -carboxyglutamic acid, peptide bonds connecting residues 6-9 (Leu, Glu, Glu, Val.) containing γ -carboxyglutamic acid, (Gla).

It has been, however, established that the drugs, coumarins and indanediones, inhibit the epoxide reductase activity and thus the formation of vitamin K-epoxide to vitamin K⁵². Once this reaction is blocked, the metabolite vitamin K-epoxide accumulating in the system, the vitamin K cycle is blocked; and because vitamin K is not regenerated and epoxide to vitamin K ratio is increased, the hydroquinone formation which is the intermediate for carboxylation is also inhibited. The concentration of vitamin K hydroquinone is decreased and carboxylase is also inhibited, whereby, the rate of conversion of prothrombin precursor to active prothrombin is diminished. However, TCP and Cl-K are antivitamin K; they may block the vitamin K, vitamin K-hydroquinone conversion,

vitamin K, vitamin K-epoxide conversion or both (Fig. 5). Accordingly, the formation of vitamin K-hydroquinone in the vitamin K cycle being inhibited by these antivitamin K, the carboxylase activity is also inhibited simultaneously. These compounds may have direct inhibitory actions on the carboxylation reaction, through their inhibitory action on carboxylase system.

The mode of action of vitamin K-hydroquinone as a redox reagent has not been established with certainty. Whether quinone-hydroquinone reaction or the hydroquinone and vitamin K-hydroperoxide system is active, has not been properly elucidated.

The requirements for the *in vitro* synthesis of prothrombin and for the vitamin K-dependent carboxylation of the glutamyl residues in microsomal prothrombin precursor are similar to the requirements for the epoxidation of vitamin K₁. Under a variety of experimental conditions carboxylation or prothrombin synthesis was never observed without simultaneous epoxidation of vitamin K₁. In addition, stimulation or inhibition of carboxylase resulted in a similar effect on epoxidation. However, one major difference between the carboxylation and epoxidation of vitamin K₁ must be emphasized. The synthesis of prothrombin can be shown to be dependent upon the concentration of bicarbonate while the epoxidation was not affected⁵⁵. If epoxidation is an obligatory molecular event for carboxylation, then either the vitamin does not act directly to transfer the carboxyl group or the mechanism may be uncoupled in the absence of bicarbonate in an analogous manner to the uncoupling of oxidative phosphorylation from electron transport in mitochondria. It may even be possible that the epoxidation reaction is not interrelated to the vitamin K-dependent carboxylation.

The Nature of the Vitamin K Intermediate :

The formation of vitamin K hydroquinone as the intermediate was suggested^{27,33} because the vitamin K hydroquinone could substitute for NADH for epoxidation, prothrombin synthesis, and carboxylation. The extent of hydroquinone formation was not established. Both prothrombin synthesis and epoxidation were shown to be dependent on molecular O₂, and the O₂ incorporation study⁵⁵ indicated that the oxygen of the epoxide ring comes from molecular oxygen rather than from water. The requirement of O₂ for prothrombin synthesis when vitamin K hydroquinone is used, is in disagreement with the report of Girardot *et al.*⁵⁶ that the requirement for molecular oxygen is eliminated when the hydroquinone is used to drive the carboxylation. The epoxidase activity was strongly inhibited by TCP or Cl-K. Warfarin at low concentrations did not inhibit the reaction, but Bell & Stark⁵⁷ have reported that, at high concentrations, warfarin and other coumarins are able to inhibit epoxidation. The

concentration used in their studies suggests that warfarin does not inhibit epoxidation of vitamin K *in vivo* at doses used to block prothrombin synthesis.

The formation of vitamin K epoxide from vitamin K hydroquinone and O_2 is an internal monooxygenase reaction, and if this formation is related to the carboxylation reaction, it is likely that reducing equivalents from other sources would be needed to enable the vitamin K competitor, tertiary butyl hydroperoxide, when used to drive the carboxylation⁵⁴. One hypothesis⁵⁸ for epoxide formation has been that H_2O_2 generated from the oxidation of the vitamin hydroquinone would be used to form the epoxide. The lack of inhibition by catalase in this system⁵⁴ would tend to argue against this possibility unless it is assumed that an extremely tight and specifically enzyme bound H_2O_2 is generated.

These data do not suggest any unequivocal molecular role for vitamin K during the carboxylation. Epoxide formation from a vitamin K hydroperoxide could generate a basic oxygen species that would then act to abstract the γ -proton of the glutamyl residues, leaving a carbanion for CO_2 attack. Such a reaction would undoubtedly require neutralization of the negatively charged carboxylate ion by the enzyme. The role of the hard acid like Ca^{2+} can be conceived. This would not however, explain the NADPH requirement. It is also conceivable that the hydroperoxide would be used to form a peracid ester of the glutamyl residue to be carboxylated. Vitamin hydroperoxide is acting in some manner to activate reaction for the incorporation of CO_2 . It is possible that the active species could be a hydroperoxide radical and that hydrogen removal via a radical mechanism may be involved⁵⁴.

If the hypothesis that epoxide formation as evidenced by Bell & Matschiner⁵⁹ is accepted to be mediated via hydroquinone formation, the carboxylase reaction is supposed to be mediated via a different route, i.e., through the formation of hydroperoxide. Accepting the hypothesis that the hydroquinone is the intermediate during epoxidation and that is the species which incorporates molecular O_2 , it may not be impossible that two oxidation-reduction processes and different redox couples, viz., vitamin K, vitamin K-hydroquinone and vitamin K, vitamin K-hydroperoxide are operative in the two processes of epoxidation and carboxylation reactions. Further studies only will establish the form of vitamin K and the molecular species involved along with the carboxylase system during the incorporation of carboxyl group in the fragment I of prothrombin and its physiological activity for its conversion to thrombin.

Conclusion :

Although the details of vitamin K-dependent reaction which leads to the carboxylation at the

γ -carbon atom of the ten glutamic acid residues located in the region 1-42 of the N-terminal region of the prothrombin molecule are not completely understood, it is clear that the postribosomal modification occurs in the liver after the completion of the synthesis of the polypeptide chain of the precursor molecule and that the action of vitamin K is not in the genetic level as was originally believed⁶⁰. Obviously, the activity of the vitamin K antagonists, coumarin and indanedione group of drugs, lies in their effects in modifying the carboxylation reaction and subsequent metal-binding properties of the molecule⁶¹, and not in mutating the genetic code, producing a physiologically inactive prothrombin molecule. The reaction requires a carboxylase system which is probably activated either by vitamin K plus NADH or a reduced form of vitamin K as the intermediate. The exact nature of the intermediate and the molecular species involved in inducing activation kinetics of the carboxylase reaction is yet to be established.

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